

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Immunopharmacological evaluation of *Phallus impudicus* against specific protein antigen

Amit Gupta^{1*}, Bharat Shinde^{1,2}

¹ Department of Immunology and Virology, Vidya Pratishthan's School of Biotechnology (VSBT, Research Centre affiliated to Savitribai Phule Pune University) Baramati, Maharashtra, India

² Vidya Pratishthan's (Principal) Arts, Science and Commerce College, Baramati, Maharashtra, India

*Corresponding Author: Amit Gupta, Ass. Prof., Senior Scientist, E-mail: amitvsbt@gmail.com; amitgupta@vsbt.res.in

ABSTRACT

The objective of our study is to examine its immunopharmacological property of stinkhorn i.e. *Phallus impudicus* against hepatitis B vaccine containing surface antigen (HBsAg; 20 µg/ml) and weak antigen ovalbumin (OVA; 100 µg/well). For these studies, *Phallus impudicus* were macerated in liquid nitrogen to prepare fine powder and measured its protein content in presence and absence (using Tris HCl and ice cold acetone) of phosphate buffered saline (PBS) which is determined through Nanodrop method. In addition, aqueous solution and protein of *Phallus impudicus* were used for determining antibody (IgG) production through indirect Elisa and also examined Th1 (TNF alpha) and Th2 (IL-4) cytokines in animal (especially Swiss mice) model studies. The results showed that *Phallus impudicus* showed more protein content in case of aqueous solution containing PBS as compared to Tris HCl and ice cold acetone. In continuation of these studies, the results showed that aqueous solution containing PBS and protein (using Tris HCl and ice cold acetone) showed declined in anti-HBsAg and anti-OVA IgG titre at higher doses as compared to standard. In addition, both of them enormously enhanced in Th1 cytokine especially TNF alpha but there is slightly observed in case of IL-4 containing HBsAg and OVA at higher doses. In short, protein and aqueous solution of *Phallus impudicus* provides preliminary information related to anticancer activity because of enhancement of TNF alpha.

Keywords: *Phallus impudicus*; Aqueous solution; Protein; Interferon; Tumor necrosis factor.

OPEN ACCESS

Citation: Gupta A, Shinde B. Immunopharmacological evaluation of *Phallus impudicus* against specific protein antigen. MicroMed. 2016; 4(2): 55-59.

DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.163673>

Received: August 19, 2016

Revised: September 20, 2016

Accepted: October 05, 2016

Copyright: © 2016 Gupta A, et al. This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited. www.journals.tmkarpinski.com/index.php/mmed

Transparency declaration: The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical approval: All these studies were conducted under IBSC guidelines and approved through Savitribai Phule Pune University, India.

INTRODUCTION

According to the literature, natural products are rich source of therapeutic agents and inspired the researchers to work on these natural products with advancement in synthetic methodologies and tried to synthesize or produce analogues of natural compound with improved immunopharmacological properties [1, 2]. Out of these

natural products, fungi represents one of them and contained rich source of novel organic compounds with interesting immunobiological properties [3, 4]. Identification of these bioactive molecules from these fungi through high throughput screening e.g. ergoflavin isolated from an endophytic fungus showed anti-inflammatory and anti-cancer activity [4].

One of the common and widely distributed

stinkhorn i.e. *Phallus impudicus* (size 15 cm; family *Phallaceae*) is normally found in lawns, garden, cultivated area, wooden part etc. This species are growing alone in summer and/or spring season but this species is identified on the basis of volva i.e. white in colour [5-9]. In contrast, this species is also identified through tip which is covered at the top with foul smelling. Despite its foul smell, this species is not poisonous and the young mushroom is consumed in parts of European countries especially France and Germany [5-8]. One of the study that claimed about the extracts of *Phallus impudicus* are responsible for inhibiting the incident rate of platelet aggregation. As per the literature, number of volatile compounds (59 in number) are reported from various classes of compounds including hydrocarbons, alcohols, aldehydes, ketones, acids, esters, terpenoids, sulfuric compounds and others at different stages of its maturity i.e. mature fruit bodies (Dimethyl trisulfide, cis- β -ocimene, trans- β -ocimene, 2-phenylacetaldehyde and 2-phenylethanol); foul odor of stinkhorn fruit bodies (dimethyl oligosulfides) etc. [5-9]. In the present study, we focused on the aqueous solution and protein content of *Phallus impudicus* for determining its effect on Th1 and Th2 type of cytokines and also estimated antibody titre against HBsAg and OVA.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection of samples

Stinkhorn fruit body of *Phallus impudicus* (weight 7.5 g) was collected from the garden of Vidya Pratishthan's Arts, Science and Commerce College, Baramati. The fungus was identified by Dr Bharat Shinde, Principal Vidya Pratishthan. After identification of this sample was used for immunological studies.

Aqueous extract preparation and estimated protein content

Phallus impudicus (5 g) was taken and macerated in liquid nitrogen (-196°C) using mortar and pestle to make fine powder. This powder was dissolved in 50 ml of PBS solution in order to get stock solution i.e. 100 mg/ml. In addition, extraction of protein, weigh 2.5 g of *Phallus impudicus* and dissolved in double amount of extraction buffer (i.e. 20 mM Tris HCl) in PBS (pH 7.2). Incubate the powder of *Phallus impudicus* along with extraction buffer for 5-7 minutes at room temperature and then centrifuged at 5500 rpm for 10 minutes at 4°C. Collect the supernatant after centrifuging and then add similar proportion of ice cold acetone. Incubate the powder solution for 8-10 minutes at room temperature and then centrifugation at corresponding speed and time. After

centrifuging, collect the pellet and washed with ice cold acetone to expel the pigments as well as lipids [10, 11]. Finally, the protein concentration was resolved through Nano drop method.

ELISA

Indirect Elisa was performed using standard HBsAg (1:1000 dilution) and weak antigen Ovalbumin (100 μ g/well) as coating antigen. Aqueous solution of *Phallus impudicus* and isolated protein were used for determination of antibody (IgG) titre. Horse anti-serum used as secondary antibody and optical density measured at 450 nm [12].

Ex vivo investigation of Th1 (TNF alpha) and Th2 (IL-4) cytokines

Briefly, Swiss mice (n=5) were immunized with aqueous solution and protein (5 mg/ml) on day 0. On day 4, spleen cells were collected and treated with variable concentration of aqueous solution and protein separately. After 24 h incubation, cell culture supernatant was collected and estimated Th1 and Th2 cytokines.

Briefly, 100 μ l of diluted capture antibody of anti-mouse TNF alpha and IL-4 was added to each well in a 96 well plate and was allowed to adhere overnight for 4°C. Plates were washed and blocked with 1X PBS supplemented with 10 % FBS for 1 h at room temperature. After washing, add serial dilutions of aqueous solution and protein supernatant of *Phallus impudicus* in the plates and then incubated for 2 h at room temperature. Washed the plates and prepared detector solution (i.e. detector antibody and avidin-horse radish peroxidase reagent) was added into each well. Finally, plates were sealed and incubated for 1 h at room temperature. After washing, 100 μ l of tri-methyl benzidine (TMB) substrate was added into each well [13, 14]. Stop solution (2 N H₂SO₄) was finally added after incubation in the dark for 30 min at room temperature. The absorbance was read at 450 nm.

Statistical analysis

The difference between control and aqueous solution including protein of *Phallus impudicus* is determined by Bonferroni multiple comparison test (One way ANOVA test).

RESULTS

Protein content

As shown in Fig. 1, data revealed the presence of protein

content in aqueous solution of *Phallus impudicus*. Similarly, isolation of protein (using Tris HCl and ice cold acetone) from *Phallus impudicus* were also measured.

ELISA

As shown in Fig. 2, the data showed that aqueous solution including protein of *Phallus impudicus*, both of them revealed maximum inhibition in IgG antibody titre at higher doses as compared to standard.

Th1 and Th2 cytokines

As shown in Fig. 3, the data showed that aqueous solution including protein of *Phallus impudicus*, both of them revealed the enhancement of Th1 and Th2 cytokines especially TNF alpha and IL-4 at higher doses as compared to standard and control.

Figure 1. Nanodrop results of aqueous solution and protein of *Phallus impudicus*.

Figure 2. ELISA. Indirect Elisa was performed using standard HBsAg vaccine (1:1000 dilution) and Ovalbumin (OVA, 100 µg/well) as coating antigen. Aqueous solution and protein of *Phallus impudicus*, anti-HBsAg and anti-OVA serum were used as standard for the estimation of anti-HBsAg and anti-OVA antibody titre. Horse anti-serum used as secondary antibody and optical density measured at 450 nm. The difference between the control and standard including aqueous solution and protein is determined by one way ANOVA test. *P<0.05; **P<0.01 and ***P<0.001.

Figure 3. Th1 and Th2 cytokines. Cells were cultured for 48 h along with variable doses of aqueous solution and protein of *Phallus impudicus*. After incubation, cell culture supernatant was collected for estimation of TNF alpha and IL-4 cytokines in HBsAg and OVA stimulated cells. The results are presented as Mean ± S.E. The difference between control, standard and aqueous leaves extract is determined through one way ANOVA test. P values: *P < 0.05, **P < 0.01, ***P < 0.001.

DISCUSSION

Bioactive molecules from various fungi that are reported and showed immunopharmacological properties especially anticancer. This property could be due to the presence of low molecular weight compounds that are present in the fungi which interfered with signal transduction pathways and provide or showed some success rate against cancer. Number of fungal metabolites based studies are already in process related to NF-κB pathway, which seems to be a promising approach in the therapy of cancer [15]. Thus the activities of various fungal species are under investigation in order to establish potent fungal metabolites especially protein that can be reliable therapeutics for humans. In the present study, we discussed about immunopharmacological activity of stinkhorn i.e. *Phallus impudicus* against specific protein antigen i.e. HBsAg and OVA for determining antibody production and also analysed Th1 (TNF alpha) and Th2 (IL-4) cytokines in animal model studies.

Ex vivo immunopharmacological studies of aqueous solution and protein of *Phallus impudicus* was evaluated in animal model studies especially Swiss mice. Intraperitoneal administration of aqueous solution and

protein resulted in significant reduction in IgG titre against HBsAg and OVA antigen. In mice, pre-existing antigen specific antibody molecule binds to the administered aqueous solution or protein of *Phallus impudicus*, the resulting immune complexes are formed and removed through mononuclear phagocyte system especially kupffer cells in the liver and protein being removed from the body through phagocytosis pathway [15]. In this study, there is decline in antibody titre at higher doses but small fraction of aqueous solution or protein of *Phallus impudicus* remaining in the cell culture supernatant. These studies are further continued with reference to Th1 and Th2 cytokines. Extension of these immunological findings to disease-related immunogens may yield effective antigen specific treatments of human allergy and autoimmune diseases [5-8].

Cell-mediated immunity through Th1 type of immunity against fungal infections, characterized by TNF alpha and Th2 characterized by IL-4. Uncontrolled Th1 and Th2 responses lead to cause autoimmune disease and allergic response [13, 14]. TNF alpha is an extraordinarily pleiotropic cytokine and played an important role in inflammation, host defence mechanism etc. Depending upon this processes, TNF alpha showed diverse effect with respect to apoptosis, necrosis, angiogenesis, cell migration etc. [13, 14]. In this study, we showed that aqueous solution and protein, both of them showed enormously enhancement in TNF alpha as compared to standard and control. In other words, *in vivo* recombinant TNF alpha directly injected or released into the tumours that ultimately destroys the tumour vasculature and blocked blood flowing pathway, inducing congestion and haemorrhage of tumour vasculature [15]. In this study, higher levels of cytokines are generally known to impair host resistance to this fungus (IL-4) were increased, whereas those critically involved in host control (TNF alpha) were either increased or unaltered depending on where they were measured. This finding establishes that overexpression of IL-4 can perturb protective immunity to this fungus even when protective cytokines are elevated in the absence of exposure to foreign antigen or pathogens.

CONCLUSION

Overexpression of IL-4 and TNF alpha in splenocyte cell culture supernatant resulted in an impaired immune response. This defect is unlikely to be caused by diminished levels of TNF alpha or IL-4 or by a global alteration in phagocyte killing function. Extensive research with *Phallus impudicus* may contribute to the discovery of new anticancer strategies.

AUTHORS' CONTRIBUTIONS

This work was carried out in collaboration between two authors. AG designed the study, wrote the protocol and interpreted the data; anchored the field study, gathered the initial data and performed preliminary data analysis. AG and BS managed the literature searches and produced the initial draft. Both the authors read and approved the final manuscript.

COMPETING INTERESTS

Authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We would also like to thank our organization (Vidya Pratishtan's School of Biotechnology) for conducting these studies.

REFERENCES

1. Russo P, Frustaci A, Del Bufalo A, Fini M, Cesario A. Multitarget drugs of plants origin acting on Alzheimer's disease. *Curr Med Chem*. 2013; 20(13): 1686-1693.
2. Lahlou M. Screening of natural products for drug discovery. *Expert Opin Drug Discov*. 2007; 2(5): 697-705.
3. Badiie P, Kordbacheh P, Alborzi A, Zeini F, Mirhendy H, Mahmoody M. Fungal infections in solid organ recipients. *Exp Clin Transplant*. 2005; 3: 385-389.
4. Deshmukh SK, Mishra PD, Almeida AK, Verekar SA, Sahoo MR, Periyasamy G, et al. Anti-inflammatory and anticancer activity of ergoflavin isolated from an endophytic fungus. *Chem Biodiv*. 2009; 7: 784.
5. Sleeman DP, Jones P, Cronin JN. Investigations of an association between the stinkhorn fungus and badger setts. *J Nat Hist*. 1996; 31(6): 983-992.
6. Anna-Karin BK, Finn OE, Rikard UC. Dimethyl oligosulphides, major volatiles released from *Sauromatum guttatum* and *Phallus impudicus*. *Phytochemistry*. 1994; 35(2): 321-323.
7. Kuznecov G, Jegina K, Kuznecovs S, Kuznecovs I. *Phallus impudicus* in thromboprophylaxis in breast cancer patients undergoing chemotherapy and hormonal treatment. *Breast*. 2007; 16(S1): S56.
8. Andersson O. The distribution and ecology of *Phallus impudicus* in the Nordic countries. *Svensk Botanisk Tidskrift*. 1989; 83(4): 219-241.
9. Niksic M, Hadzic I, Glisic M. Is *Phallus impudicus* a mycological giant? *Mycologist*. 2004; 18(1): 21-22.
10. Gupta A, Shah AP, Chabukswar AR, Chaphalkar SR. Extraction of proteases from leaves of *Mimusops elengi* and its immunopharmacological applications. *Indo Am J Pharmac Sci*. 2016; 3(3): 211-220.
11. Gupta A, Shah AP, Chabukswar AR, Chaphalkar SR. Immunopharmacological exploration of proteases from

- Catharanthus roseus* on virally infected human whole blood. J Dis Global Health. 2016; 6(1): 36-42.
12. Gupta A, Chaphalkar SR. Immunoadjuvant potential of *Azadirachta indica* against rabies, hepatitis and DPT vaccine antigen. Int J Med Pharmac Sci. 2015; 5(7): 1-5.
 13. Gupta A, Khajuria A, Singh J, Bedi KL, Satti NK, Dutt P, et al. Immunomodulatory activity of biopolymeric fraction RLJ-NE-205 from *Picrorhiza kurroa*. Int Immunopharmacol. 2006; 6(10): 1543-1549.
 14. Gupta A, Khajuria A, Singh J, Singh S, Suri KA, Qazi GN. Immunological adjuvant effect of *Boswellia serrata* (BOS 2000) on specific antibody and cellular response to ovalbumin in mice. Int Immunopharmacol. 2011; 11(8): 968-975.
 15. Petrova RD, Mahajna J, Reznick AZ, Wasser SP, Denchev CM, Nevo E. Fungal substances as modulators of NF-kappa B activation pathway. Mol Biol Rep. 2007; 34(3): 145-154.